

A Biot-Savart Formulation for the Magnetic Field of a Finite-Length Solenoid

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Abstract. A closed-form integral expression for the magnetic field of a finite solenoid at any point in space was derived. Using the Biot-Savart law in cylindrical coordinates, we obtained formulas for the radial and axial field components. Further analysis confirmed the solution reduces to known special cases and numerical evaluation showed the presence of fringe fields and an external field absent in the infinite-solenoid approximation.

Keywords— Magnetism, Magnetostatics, Biot-Savart law, Solenoid, Fringe fields, Elliptic integrals, Maxwell's equations

1. Introduction

Textbooks commonly introduce the magnetic field of an infinite solenoid [1], but the magnetic field of a finite-length solenoid is often not mentioned. This is because with an infinite solenoid, a perfectly uniform magnetic field is confined in its interior, with a magnitude of $B = \mu_0 n I$, and has zero field outside. Thanks to cylindrical symmetry, this formula can easily be derived using Ampère's law: $\oint \mathbf{B} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\ell} = \mu_0 I$ [2]. While this approximation is useful, no real-world solenoid can be infinite in length. This introduces fringe fields at the ends, making the internal field non-uniform and creating an external field.

Figure 1: A solenoid.

The magnetic field for any configuration of steady currents is determined by the Biot-Savart law. This law states that for a thin wire the magnetic field $d\mathbf{B}$ created by a small segment of wire carrying current I is proportional to I , the length of the segment $d\boldsymbol{\ell}$, and the sine of the angle between the wire and the line to the point of measurement, and inversely proportional to the square of the distance r [3]. The total field is found by integrating along all current paths:

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{I d\boldsymbol{\ell} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}}{r^2}. \quad (1)$$

Using Biot-Savart's law to a real-world geometry like a finite solenoid is very hard, especially because lacks translational symmetry unlike an infinite solenoid. Most resources stop at calculating

the field only along the solenoid's central axis where symmetry makes the problem simpler. The much more challenging part of finding the field at any arbitrary point (ρ, z) in space is hard to find.

The goal of this work was to do the much more challenging part. The Biot-Savart law was used to derive a complete integral expression for the magnetic field vector $\mathbf{B}(\rho, z)$ of a finite-length solenoid with radius R and length L . A formula that is valid at any point inside, outside, or near the end of the solenoid was found.

2. Mathematical Background

This section contains the essential mathematic concepts required for the derivation and interpretation.

2.1. The Cylindrical Coordinate System

A point in space is defined by three coordinates: ρ , the radial distance from the z -axis ($\rho \geq 0$); ϕ , the azimuthal angle, measured from the positive x -axis ($0 \leq \phi < 2\pi$); and z , the vertical coordinate, identical to that in Cartesian coordinates. The relationship to Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) is given by:

$$x = \rho \cos \phi. \quad (2)$$

$$y = \rho \sin \phi. \quad (3)$$

$$z = z. \quad (4)$$

The unit vectors $\hat{\rho}$, $\hat{\phi}$, \hat{z} point in the direction of increasing ρ , ϕ , and z , respectively. Unlike Cartesian unit vectors, the directions of $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ are functions of the azimuthal angle ϕ and therefore change depending on the point in space:

$$\hat{\rho} = \cos \phi \hat{x} + \sin \phi \hat{y}. \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{\phi} = -\sin \phi \hat{x} + \cos \phi \hat{y}. \quad (6)$$

$$\hat{z} = \hat{z}. \quad (7)$$

2.2. Vector Operations

The dot product (or scalar product) of two vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is defined as:

$$\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B} = A_x B_x + A_y B_y + A_z B_z = |\mathbf{A}| |\mathbf{B}| \cos \theta. \quad (8)$$

where θ is the angle between the two vectors. The result is a scalar. Geometrically, it measures the extent to which the two vectors point in the same direction. Work, which you may have learned in basic physics, is actually the dot product of the force vector and the displacement vector.

The cross product (or vector product) of two vectors \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B} &= \begin{vmatrix} \hat{x} & \hat{y} & \hat{z} \\ A_x & A_y & A_z \\ B_x & B_y & B_z \end{vmatrix} = (A_y B_z - A_z B_y) \hat{x} + (A_z B_x - A_x B_z) \hat{y} + (A_x B_y - A_y B_x) \hat{z} \\ &= |\mathbf{A}| |\mathbf{B}| \sin \theta \hat{n}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The result is a new vector that is orthogonal (in other words, perpendicular) to the plane formed by \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} . The magnitude of the cross product equals the area of the parallelogram spanned by the two vectors. Torque, another concept from basic physics, is the cross product between the force vector and the position vector.

2.3. Integration of Vector Fields

To calculate magnetic fields, we must use the calculus of vector fields. A vector field assigns a vector to every point in space, such as the familiar gravitational field \mathbf{g} or the magnetic field \mathbf{B} . The Biot-Savart law requires us to sum (integrate) contributions along a path. This is basically a line integral. A line integral involves integrating a function along a curve in space.

Consider a path C through space, and a scalar function $f(x, y, z)$ defined on that path. The line integral of f along C is denoted by:

$$\int_C f(x, y, z) ds, \quad (10)$$

where ds is an infinitesimal element of arc length along the path C . This integral represents the sum of the values of f at every point on the curve.

More importantly for magnetism, we can integrate a vector field along a path. This is very important for calculating the magnetic field (a vector field) from a current. The line integral of a vector field \mathbf{F} along a curve C is defined as:

$$\int_C \mathbf{F} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\ell}. \quad (11)$$

Here, $d\boldsymbol{\ell}$ is an infinitesimal vector element tangent to the path C . The dot product $\mathbf{F} \cdot d\boldsymbol{\ell}$ gives the component of \mathbf{F} that is parallel to the path. This integral measures the net effect of the field along the path.

The Biot-Savart law (Equation 1) is a special type of vector integral. For each segment $d\boldsymbol{\ell}$ of the wire, we calculate its cross product with the unit vector $\hat{\mathbf{r}}$. The integral then represents the vector sum of all these infinitesimal contributions $d\mathbf{B}$ to the total magnetic field.

2.4. Vector Operators

The fundamental operations of vector calculus are the gradient, divergence, and curl. These operators describe how a field changes from point to point.

The gradient (∇f) operates on a scalar function $f(x, y, z)$ and produces a vector field that points in the direction of the greatest rate of increase of f . Its magnitude is the slope of the function in that direction. In Cartesian coordinates, it is given by:

$$\nabla f = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x} \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial y} \hat{\mathbf{y}} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (12)$$

The divergence ($\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F}$) operates on a vector field \mathbf{F} and produces a scalar function. Intuitively, think of a positive divergence as a source of water while a negative divergence as a sink. In Cartesian coordinates, it is:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} = \frac{\partial F_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial F_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial F_z}{\partial z}. \quad (13)$$

The curl ($\nabla \times \mathbf{F}$) also operates on a vector field and produces another vector field. It measures the infinitesimal rotation of the field around a point. Imagine a tiny paddlewheel placed in the water

flow represented by the vector field; the curl tells you how strongly and in what axis the paddlewheel would spin. In Cartesian coordinates, it is given by the determinant:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}} & \hat{\mathbf{y}} & \hat{\mathbf{z}} \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial x} & \frac{\partial}{\partial y} & \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \\ F_x & F_y & F_z \end{vmatrix} = \left(\frac{\partial F_z}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial F_y}{\partial z} \right) \hat{\mathbf{x}} - \left(\frac{\partial F_z}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial F_x}{\partial z} \right) \hat{\mathbf{y}} + \left(\frac{\partial F_y}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial F_x}{\partial y} \right) \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (14)$$

2.5. Vector Calculus in Cylindrical Coordinates

The unit vectors $\hat{\rho}$ and $\hat{\phi}$ are not constant; their direction depends on the coordinates of the point. This must be accounted for when taking derivatives and integrating.

The line integral of a vector field, introduced in Section 2.3, requires an infinitesimal displacement vector $d\ell$. In cylindrical coordinates, this vector is:

$$d\ell = d\rho \hat{\rho} + \rho d\phi \hat{\phi} + dz \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (15)$$

The factor of ρ in the $\hat{\phi}$ component makes sure that the units are consistent, as $d\phi$ is dimensionless. This expression for $d\ell$ will be used when applying the Biot-Savart law to our solenoid.

The formulas for the essential vector operators in cylindrical coordinates are as follows.

The gradient of a scalar function $f(\rho, \phi, z)$ is:

$$\nabla f = \frac{\partial f}{\partial \rho} \hat{\rho} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial f}{\partial \phi} \hat{\phi} + \frac{\partial f}{\partial z} \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (16)$$

Notice the factor of $1/\rho$ in the $\hat{\phi}$ -component. This serves a similar purpose of making sure that the units are consistent.

The divergence of a vector field $\mathbf{F} = F_\rho \hat{\rho} + F_\phi \hat{\phi} + F_z \hat{\mathbf{z}}$ is:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{F} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial(\rho F_\rho)}{\partial \rho} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial F_\phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial F_z}{\partial z}. \quad (17)$$

The first term expands to $\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial(\rho F_\rho)}{\partial \rho} = \frac{\partial F_\rho}{\partial \rho} + \frac{F_\rho}{\rho}$, which is responsible for how a radial field spreads naturally even if its magnitude is constant.

The curl of the vector field \mathbf{F} is:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \left(\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial F_z}{\partial \phi} - \frac{\partial F_\phi}{\partial z} \right) \hat{\rho} + \left(\frac{\partial F_\rho}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial F_z}{\partial \rho} \right) \hat{\phi} + \frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial(\rho F_\phi)}{\partial \rho} - \frac{\partial F_\rho}{\partial \phi} \right) \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (18)$$

3. Derivation of the Magnetic Field

This section details the application of the Biot-Savart law to a finite solenoid of length L and radius R , with n turns per unit length carrying a current I . The solenoid is oriented along the z -axis, symmetric about the origin, such that it extends from $z = -L/2$ to $z = +L/2$.

3.1. Modeling the Solenoid as a Surface Current

A solenoid is a helix. However, for the purpose of calculating the magnetic field at a point not immediately near the wires, we may approximate it as a series of N distinct, concentric circular loops. In the limit of tightly wound turns, this model becomes exact. We therefore consider the solenoid to

be a cylindrical surface current. The surface current density \mathbf{K} , representing amperes per unit length perpendicular to the flow, is azimuthal and has a magnitude given by the total current per unit length along z :

$$K = nI. \quad (19)$$

Thus, the surface current density vector is $\mathbf{K} = nI\hat{\phi}'$. Now, apply the Biot-Savart law, we must integrate over this current distribution. The standard Biot-Savart law for a surface current is:

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{(\mathbf{K} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}})}{r^2} da', \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_{\text{field}} - \mathbf{r}_{\text{source}}$ is the vector from the source point on the solenoid to the observation point, and da' is an infinitesimal area element on the solenoid [4].

3.2. Parameterization of the Source

We now parameterize the source points \mathbf{r}' on the cylindrical surface of the solenoid. A given point is defined by its axial coordinate z' and its azimuthal angle ϕ' . The coordinates of the source point are:

$$x' = R \cos \phi'. \quad (21)$$

$$y' = R \sin \phi'. \quad (22)$$

$$z' = z'. \quad (23)$$

The corresponding position vector is:

$$\mathbf{r}' = R \cos \phi' \hat{\mathbf{x}} + R \sin \phi' \hat{\mathbf{y}} + z' \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (24)$$

The infinitesimal area element on the cylindrical surface is:

$$da' = (Rd\phi')(dz') = R d\phi' dz'. \quad (25)$$

The surface current vector at this point is purely azimuthal:

$$\mathbf{K} = nI\hat{\phi}' = nI(-\sin \phi' \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \cos \phi' \hat{\mathbf{y}}). \quad (26)$$

3.3. The Vector \mathbf{r} and its Magnitude

The observation point, using cylindrical symmetry, can be placed in the x - z plane ($\phi = 0$) without loss of generality. Its position vector is:

$$\mathbf{r} = \rho \cos(0) \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \rho \sin(0) \hat{\mathbf{y}} + z \hat{\mathbf{z}} = \rho \hat{\mathbf{x}} + z \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (27)$$

The vector from the source to the observation point is therefore:

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_{\text{field}} - \mathbf{r}_{\text{source}} = (\rho - R \cos \phi') \hat{\mathbf{x}} + (0 - R \sin \phi') \hat{\mathbf{y}} + (z - z') \hat{\mathbf{z}}. \quad (28)$$

The magnitude of \mathbf{r} is:

$$r = \sqrt{(\rho - R \cos \phi')^2 + (R \sin \phi')^2 + (z - z')^2} = \sqrt{\rho^2 + R^2 - 2\rho R \cos \phi' + (z - z')^2}. \quad (29)$$

The corresponding unit vector is $\hat{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{r}/r$.

3.4. The Cross Product $\mathbf{K} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}$

The cross product in the integrand is:

$$\mathbf{K} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}} = \frac{\mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r}}{r^3}. \quad (30)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{K} = nI(-\sin \phi' \hat{\mathbf{x}} + \cos \phi' \hat{\mathbf{y}})$ and the components of \mathbf{r} , we compute the cross product via the determinant:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r} &= nI \begin{vmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{x}} & \hat{\mathbf{y}} & \hat{\mathbf{z}} \\ -\sin \phi' & \cos \phi' & 0 \\ (\rho - R \cos \phi') & (-R \sin \phi') & (z - z') \end{vmatrix} \\ &= nI \left([\cos \phi'(z - z') - 0 \cdot (-R \sin \phi')] \hat{\mathbf{x}} [(-\sin \phi')(z - z') - 0 \cdot (\rho - R \cos \phi')] \hat{\mathbf{y}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. [(-\sin \phi')(-R \sin \phi') - (\cos \phi')(\rho - R \cos \phi')] \hat{\mathbf{z}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Simplifying term-by-term for the components:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}\text{-component: } nI \cos \phi'(z - z'). \quad (32)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{y}}\text{-component: } -nI [\sin \phi'(z - z')]. \quad (33)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}\text{-component: } nI [(R \sin^2 \phi') - \rho \cos \phi' + R \cos^2 \phi'] = nI [R(\sin^2 \phi' + \cos^2 \phi') - \rho \cos \phi']. \quad (34)$$

The z-component simplifies to $nI(R - \rho \cos \phi')$ using the identity $\sin^2 \phi' + \cos^2 \phi' = 1$. Thus, the full vector is:

$$\mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r} = nI[(z - z') \cos \phi' \hat{\mathbf{x}} - (z - z') \sin \phi' \hat{\mathbf{y}} + (R - \rho \cos \phi') \hat{\mathbf{z}}]. \quad (35)$$

It is physically meaningful to express this result in cylindrical coordinates at the observation point. Noting that at $\phi = 0$, the unit vectors are $\hat{\boldsymbol{\rho}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}$ and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}} = \hat{\mathbf{y}}$, we can write:

$$\mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r} = nI[(z - z') \cos \phi' \hat{\boldsymbol{\rho}} - (z - z') \sin \phi' \hat{\boldsymbol{\phi}} + (R - \rho \cos \phi') \hat{\mathbf{z}}]. \quad (36)$$

3.5. The Final Integral Expression

We now assemble the complete integrand. The magnetic field is given by:

$$\mathbf{B}(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{\mathbf{K} \times \hat{\mathbf{r}}}{r^2} da' = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \int \frac{\mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r}}{r^3} da'. \quad (37)$$

Substituting $\mathbf{K} \times \mathbf{r}$, $r^3 = [\rho^2 + R^2 - 2\rho R \cos \phi' + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}$, and $da' = R d\phi' dz'$, we obtain the final explicit integral formula. The field components are:

$$B_\rho(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R}{4\pi} \int_{z'=-L/2}^{L/2} \int_{\phi'=0}^{2\pi} \frac{(z - z') \cos \phi'}{[\rho^2 + R^2 - 2\rho R \cos \phi' + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}} d\phi' dz'. \quad (38)$$

$$B_\phi(\rho, z) = -\frac{\mu_0 n I R}{4\pi} \int_{z'=-L/2}^{L/2} \int_{\phi'=0}^{2\pi} \frac{(z - z') \sin \phi'}{[\rho^2 + R^2 - 2\rho R \cos \phi' + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}} d\phi' dz'. \quad (39)$$

$$B_z(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R}{4\pi} \int_{z'=-L/2}^{L/2} \int_{\phi'=0}^{2\pi} \frac{(R - \rho \cos \phi')}{[\rho^2 + R^2 - 2\rho R \cos \phi' + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}} d\phi' dz'. \quad (40)$$

Equation 39 contains $\sin \phi'$ in the numerator. The integral of $\sin \phi'$ over a full period $[0, 2\pi]$ is zero. Furthermore, the rest of the integrand is an even function in ϕ' around 0. Therefore, the azimuthal component of the field vanishes and becomes:

$$B_\phi(\rho, z) = 0. \quad (41)$$

This result is expected due to the axial symmetry of the problem; the field lines lie in planes of constant ϕ . The magnetic field for a finite solenoid is therefore described by its radial and axial components, B_ρ and B_z . The expressions for B_ρ and B_z in Equations 38 and 40 constitute the objective of this work. They provide a closed-form integral solution for the magnetic field at any point (ρ, z) in space due to a finite solenoid.

4. Analysis of Results and Special Cases

4.1. The Field on the Central Axis

A standard textbook result is the magnetic field along the central axis ($\rho = 0$) of a finite solenoid. Our general result must reduce to this known case to hold true. Setting $\rho = 0$ in Equations 38 and 40 simplifies the expressions significantly.

The radial component vanishes due to the $\cos \phi'$ term in the numerator of B_ρ :

$$B_\rho(0, z) = 0. \quad (42)$$

The axial component, with $\rho = 0$, becomes:

$$B_z(0, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R}{4\pi} \int_{z'=-L/2}^{L/2} \int_{\phi'=0}^{2\pi} \frac{R}{[R^2 + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}} d\phi' dz'. \quad (43)$$

The integrand is now independent of ϕ' . The ϕ' integral is therefore trivial:

$$\int_0^{2\pi} d\phi' = 2\pi. \quad (44)$$

Substituting this yields the well-known formula:

$$B_z(0, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I R^2}{2} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \frac{dz'}{[R^2 + (z - z')^2]^{3/2}}. \quad (45)$$

This integral can be evaluated exactly. The result is the expression:

$$B_z(0, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I}{2} \left[\frac{(z + L/2)}{\sqrt{R^2 + (z + L/2)^2}} - \frac{(z - L/2)}{\sqrt{R^2 + (z - L/2)^2}} \right]. \quad (46)$$

We have demonstrated a successful reduction of our general result to this standard formula.

4.2. The Infinite Solenoid

An infinite solenoid would have the limit $L \rightarrow \infty$. In this limit, the field inside should become uniform and purely axial, while the field outside should vanish. For a point inside the solenoid ($|\rho| < R$), as $L \rightarrow \infty$, the end effects become negligible. The integrals over z' extend from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. The

resulting field must be independent of z . The radial component B_ρ must be zero due to symmetry arguments. The axial component evaluation yields the classic result:

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} B_z(\rho, z) = \mu_0 n I, \quad \text{for } \rho < R. \quad (47)$$

For a point outside the solenoid ($\rho > R$), the field vanishes in the infinite-length limit:

$$\lim_{L \rightarrow \infty} B_z(\rho, z) = 0, \quad \text{for } \rho > R. \quad (48)$$

Our integral expressions are consistent with these limits, which further confirms their correctness.

4.3. Satisfaction of Maxwell's Equations

The derived field must satisfy the static Maxwell's equations for magnetism. Gauss's Law for Magnetism states that the divergence of the magnetic field is 0 [5]:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0. \quad (49)$$

Using the expression for divergence in cylindrical coordinates (Equation 17), one can verify that the field from our integrals satisfies this law everywhere. Next, Ampère's Law in differential form, for regions outside the source current ($\mathbf{J} = 0$), states:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} = 0. \quad (50)$$

The field in a current-free region must be irrotational. Our calculated field must satisfy this outside the solenoid windings. Inside the solenoid, the curl is non-zero and proportional to the current density. The vanishing of the azimuthal component ($B_\phi = 0$) is a direct consequence of the symmetry of the source and is required by these laws for this geometry.

4.4. Off-Axis Evaluation

For points where $\rho \neq 0$, the integrals in Equations 38 and 40 cannot be reduced to a simple closed form in terms of elementary functions. The ϕ' integral can be expressed in terms of complete elliptic integrals, $K(k)$ and $E(k)$, where the modulus k is a function of ρ , R , z , and z' .

The final form of the field becomes a single integral over z' of these elliptic integrals:

$$B_z(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I}{2\pi} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \left[\frac{[R^2 - \rho^2 - (z - z')^2] E(k) + [R^2 + \rho^2 + (z - z')^2] K(k)}{[(R + \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2]^{3/2} \sqrt{(R - \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2}} \right] dz', \quad (51)$$

where $k^2 = \frac{4R\rho}{(R+\rho)^2 + (z-z')^2}$. A similar expression exists for B_ρ . While more complex, this form is significantly easier to perform numerical computation on than the original double integral, which is the subject of the next section.

5. Numerical Evaluation

The double integrals in Equations 38 and 40, while exact, are not amenable to an analytical solution for general off-axis points. Therefore, numerical computation was needed to evaluate the magnetic field and visualize its behavior.

5.1. Numerical Methods

The integration was performed using Python, using the libraries NumPy and SciPy. The axial symmetry of the problem means the field is identical for all azimuthal angles ϕ ; the calculation need only be performed in the $\phi = 0$ plane. The domain of integration is defined by the source coordinates: z' from $-L/2$ to $L/2$ and ϕ' from 0 to 2π .

For a given observation point (ρ, z) , the value of the integrand in Equations 38 and 40 was computed for each combination of (ϕ', z') . The `scipy.integrate` library's `dblquad` function was used to perform the double integration numerically. This function allows for the specification of the inner integral limits (ϕ') as functions of the outer variable (z'), though in this case the limits are constants.

To improve efficiency, the ϕ' integral was first simplified by recognizing that the integrals for B_ρ and B_z are of standard forms that can be expressed in terms of complete elliptic integrals. The expressions used were:

$$B_z(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I}{2\pi} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{(R + \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2}} \left[\frac{R^2 - \rho^2 - (z - z')^2}{(R - \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2} E(k) + K(k) \right] dz'. \quad (52)$$

$$B_\rho(\rho, z) = \frac{\mu_0 n I}{2\pi} \frac{\rho}{R} \int_{-L/2}^{L/2} \frac{(z' - z)}{\sqrt{(R + \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2}} \left[\frac{R^2 + \rho^2 + (z - z')^2}{(R - \rho)^2 + (z - z')^2} E(k) - K(k) \right] dz'. \quad (53)$$

where $k^2 = \frac{4R\rho}{(R+\rho)^2+(z-z')^2}$, and $K(k)$ and $E(k)$ are the complete elliptic integrals of the first and second kind, respectively. This reduction to a single integral over z' drastically reduces the computation time and increases accuracy.

The remaining single integral over z' was then evaluated numerically for each observation point using `scipy.integrate.quad`. The elliptic integrals were computed using `scipy.special.ellipk` and `scipy.special.ellipe`.

5.2. Results and Field Visualization

The numerical evaluation was performed for a solenoid with the following parameters: radius $R = 1$ unit, length $L = 5$ units, number of turns per unit length $n = 1000 \text{ m}^{-1}$, and current $I = 1 \text{ A}$.

Figure 2: Magnetic field B_z along the central axis of the finite solenoid.

Figure 2 shows the computed B_z component along the solenoid's axis. The field is strongest and nearly constant at the center, with a magnitude approaching $\mu_0 n I$. It decreases symmetrically towards the ends of the solenoid, confirming the expected behavior.

Figure 3: Contour plot of the magnetic field magnitude $|B|$ in the x - z plane.

Figure 3 is a contour plot of the field magnitude in a plane containing the solenoid's axis. This visualization clearly shows the three key regions: the uniform field inside the solenoid body, the spreading fringe fields at the ends, and the weak external field.

Figure 4: Vector field plot of B in the x - z plane.

Figure 4 is the vector field, showing the direction and flow of the magnetic field lines. The field loops are continuous and closed, confirming the solenoidal nature of the magnetic field ($\nabla \cdot B = 0$).

The field lines inside the solenoid are largely straight and parallel, curving smoothly as they exit the solenoid and loop around externally.

The numerical results demonstrate all the expected characteristics of a finite solenoid's magnetic field: internal uniformity, external fringe fields, and the dipolar nature of the field far from the source. The perfect agreement with the known on-axis solution provides strong validation for the numerical implementation of the off-axis formulas derived in this work.

6. Conclusion

A complete and explicit integral expression for the magnetic field of a finite solenoid was derived. Starting from the Biot-Savart law, we modeled the solenoid as a cylindrical surface current to arrive at the general formulas for the radial and axial field components, $B_\rho(\rho, z)$ and $B_z(\rho, z)$ (Equations 38 and 40).

The derived expressions demonstrated to hold true by their reduction to the well-known solution along the central axis and their consistency with the infinite solenoid. Furthermore, the results satisfy Maxwell's equations for magnetism. Evaluating the integrals for off-axis points was done through numerical computation. The subsequent visualization of the field showed the largely uniform internal field, the fringe fields at the ends, and the weak but non-zero external dipolar field, in line with the characteristics of a finite solenoid.

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